

Massive MIMO Channel Estimation using few parameters in sparse propagation environments

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Abstract—Exploring underused spectrum bands such as the mmWave band is key to solve future wireless communications necessities. This work studies the problem of channel estimation in multi-antenna systems in this high-frequency band considering the few propagation parameters that are unveiled due to the sparse propagation nature. We address the channel estimation by applying atomic norm as a gridless multidimensional spectral estimation. The applied methodology is compared in different scenarios with several on-grid spectral estimation approaches and also with traditional non-parametrical methods.

Index Terms—Channel estimation, compress sensing, massive MIMO, mmWave, ℓ_1 atomic norm

I. INTRODUCTION

Wireless communication systems in both fifth generation (5G) and the upcoming sixth generation (6G) [1] are characterized by the ability to connect multiple wireless devices at the same time, using multiple antennas in both the receiver and the transmitter (known as massive MIMO, massive multiple-input multiple-output). This system improves both energy efficiency, using the antennas together to increase the gain of the transmitted signal, and spectral efficiency, since massive MIMO enables the use the antenna array to focus the antenna beams on individual users.

Although spectral efficiency is improving significantly by using MIMO systems [2], it is still not sufficient to cover the ever-increasing number of users on the planet. It is therefore necessary to explore underutilized bands of the spectrum, such as the mmWave band (in the 30-300 GHz range). As this band of frequencies has much more capacity available [3], the bandwidth that each operator will be able to allocate will also be larger, which will enable to increase the total number of users.

Due to the sparse nature of this frequency band [4], [5], the channel matrix that characterizes the signal model used in massive MIMO systems can also be expressed as a sparse structure containing propagation direction information in multidimensional space. Sparse models are very frequent in a wide range of scientific scenarios besides signal processing [6], for example machine learning [7] or object tracking [8].

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Given the high frequency that characterizes the mmWave band, MIMO systems with a high number of antennas are needed to compensate for propagation losses [9] using signal processing techniques that need information on the channel state. However, in massive MIMO systems the availability of the channel state is particularly challenging due to the high channel dimensionality and the typical low SNR (Signal to Noise Ratio) scenarios [10].

In this work, the problem of estimating a multi-antenna channel matrix is addressed by targeting a method that unveils the parameters that define the propagation, the angle of departure (AoD) and the angle of arrival (AoA), which depend on the azimuth and elevation angles. It is therefore a multidimensional spectral estimation problem that only estimate the few propagation parameters and alongside obtain the whole estimation matrix. Several signal parameter estimation methods such as orthogonal matching pursuit (OMP) [11], multiple signal classification (MUSIC) [12] and Iterative Interference Cancellation (IIC) [13] have addressed this problem. However, the main issue of these methods is that they use an on-grid approach [14], [15], i.e., the resolution of the problem always contains a margin of error that is given by the definition of the grid itself. There are also several non-parametrical channel estimation methods for massive MIMO systems such as least squares (LS) [16] and minimum mean square error (MMSE) [17], which will also be included in this work as benchmarks.

The method proposed in this paper for the resolution of the channel matrix estimation problem is a gridless method based on the optimization of the atomic norm for the recovery of the AoD and AoA of the propagation paths that, alongside, provides an estimation of the channel matrix. To address the Atomic Norm estimation in noisy environments, we propose a novel optimization function different from the one proposed in [18], [19], that avoid the need for off-line estimation of the convex parameter that weights the different terms of the optimization function. Together with the results obtained with the proposed method, comparisons with the most relevant methods of the state of the art, mentioned above, are included.

Notation: $[\cdot]^T$ is the transpose and $[\cdot]^H$ is the Hermitian. The operator $\text{diag}(\mathbf{x})$, returns a diagonal matrix with diagonal given by \mathbf{x} . For a given integer $K \in \mathbb{Z}$, $[K] = \{1, \dots, K\}$. \mathbb{T} denotes the unit circle $[0, 1]$ by identifying the beginning and

the ending points. $\|\cdot\|_\rho$ represents the ℓ_ρ norm. The y -modulus of value x is given by $\text{mod}(x, y)$. The inner product of vectors \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} is represented with $\mathbf{x} \cdot \mathbf{y}$ and the Kronecker product is represented by \otimes .

II. SPARSE MMWAVE SIGNAL MODEL

The general signal pilot-based estimation model used in massive MIMO systems [20] can be defined as:

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{P} + \mathbf{W} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$ is the channel matrix with a sparse structure, due to the nature of the mmWave band. Since $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$ has this sparse structure, the observations $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times P}$ will represent a sparse mmWave signal model. The dimensions of $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$ depend on the number of the elements in the transmitter and the receiver, M and N respectively. $\mathbf{P} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times P}$ is the matrix that contains the P -length sequence of complex pilots, which are previously known, and $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times P}$ is a matrix whose elements represent additive white Gaussian noise with σ_w^2 variance.

Since $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$ depends on the antennas in both the transmitter and the receiver, we can define the antenna vectors $\mathbf{M} = [M_1, \dots, M_{d_t}]$ and $\mathbf{N} = [N_1, \dots, N_{d_r}]$, that are going to characterize the number of radiating elements deployed in each of the dimensions of the uniform array. The dimensionality of the antenna arrays is $d_t \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ and $d_r \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ for the transmitter and the receiver, respectively. The radiating elements of each dimension are uniformly spaced at a normalized distance δ_i . We can also define the normalized position of the m -th antenna as $\mathbf{m}_m = [m_m^1, \dots, m_m^d]^\top$ deployed in d dimensions, where d refers to d_t or d_r depending if the antenna is placed at the transmitter or receiver side.

The sensing capabilities depend on the number of spatial dimensions to be explored. For only one dimension, $d=1$, the azimuth angle $\theta \in [0, \pi]$ is the only relevant propagation direction. For $d=2$, besides the azimuth angle $\theta \in [0, \pi]$, the elevation angle $\phi \in [-\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2}]$ propagation direction is needed. In the $d=3$ case, there is full spherical characterization with azimuth $\theta \in [0, 2\pi]$ and elevation $\phi \in [-\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2}]$. Focussing on the transmitter, in order to contain the information related to the propagation, we can define a normalized frequency parameter vector $\mathbf{g} = [g^1, \dots, g^{d_t}]^\top \in \mathbb{T}^{d_t}$, which depends on the dimensionality of the array deployment.

$$g^{d_t} = \begin{cases} g^1 = \text{mod}(\delta_1 \cos \theta, 1) & d_t = 1 \\ g^2 = \text{mod}(\delta_2 \sin \theta \sin \phi, 1) & d_t = 2 \\ g^3 = \text{mod}(\delta_3 \sin \theta \cos \phi, 1) & d_t = 3 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Now that we have defined the frequency parameter vector \mathbf{g} and the normalized position vector for the m -th antenna \mathbf{m}_m , we can define the steering vector of the d -dimensional uniform array. The one associated to the transmitter can be expressed as follows:

$$\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{M}}(\mathbf{g}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{M}} [e^{j2\pi\mathbf{g} \cdot \mathbf{m}_1}, \dots, e^{j2\pi\mathbf{g} \cdot \mathbf{m}_M}]^\top \quad (3)$$

Similarly we can define an equivalent vector to \mathbf{g} associated to the receiver, $\mathbf{f} = [f^1, \dots, f^{d_r}]^\top \in \mathbb{T}^{d_r}$, and a steering vector $\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{N}}(\mathbf{f})$, so that \mathbf{g} and \mathbf{f} are normalized frequency parameter vectors that contains information of the AoA and AoD respectively.

Once we have defined the complete structure of the steering vectors for both the receiver and the transmitter, we can finally express the channel matrix $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$, which sparse structure aims to represent the nature of the narrowband stationary mmWave band scenario that we are studying:

$$\mathbf{H}(-\mathbf{g}_{1:K}, \mathbf{f}_{1:K}) = \sum_{k=1}^K \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{N}}(\mathbf{f}_k) \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{M}}^H(-\mathbf{g}_k) \quad (4)$$

where $1 \leq k \leq K$ is the propagation path, with K being the number of scatters of the scenario.

Low-key channel estimation focuses on estimating the channel coefficients or channel matrix $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$ from a set of observations $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times P}$ received after the transmission of a previously known P -length sequence of complex pilots, which are previously known. Considering the noisy stationary mmWave propagation scenario defined in (1), we can now express it as a parametrical model:

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{H}(\ell_{1:K})\mathbf{P} + \mathbf{W} \quad (5)$$

where we define the set of frequencies $\ell_{1:K} = \{\ell_1, \ell_2, \dots, \ell_K\}$ so that $\mathbf{H}(-\mathbf{g}_{1:K}, \mathbf{f}_{1:K}) = \mathbf{H}(\ell_{1:K})$. This set of frequencies $\ell_{1:K}$, that allows the characterization of AoA and AoD, contains linearly independent and identically distributed random vectors.

The parametrical signal model in 5 can be vectorized as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{y} = \text{vec}(\mathbf{Y}) &= (\mathbf{P}^\top \otimes \mathbf{I}_N) \mathbf{h}(\ell_{1:K}) + \mathbf{w} \\ &= \mathbf{Q}\mathbf{h}(\ell_{1:K}) + \mathbf{w} \\ &= \mathbf{Q} \sum_{k=1}^K \gamma_k \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{T}}(\ell_k) + \mathbf{w} = \mathbf{Q}\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{T}}(\ell_{1:K})\boldsymbol{\gamma} + \mathbf{w} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where, if we define $T = MN$, the steering vector $\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{T}}(\ell_k) \in \mathbb{C}^T$ is formed by the Kronecker product of the steering vectors associated to the receiver and the transmitter, respectively, $\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{M}}^*(\mathbf{g}_k) \otimes \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{N}}(\mathbf{f}_k)$. $[\mathbf{M}, \mathbf{N}] = \mathbf{T} = [M_1, \dots, M_{d_t}, N_1, \dots, N_{d_r}] = [\mathbf{T}_1, \dots, \mathbf{T}_{d_t}]$. We can also find in (6) the expression for the vectorized channel matrix $\mathbf{h}(\ell_{1:K}) = \text{vec}(\mathbf{H}(\ell_{1:K})) = \sum_{k=1}^K \gamma_k \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{T}}(\ell_k)$, where $\boldsymbol{\gamma} = [\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_K]^\top$ are the fading coefficients of the channel, $\mathbf{w} = \text{vec}(\mathbf{W}) \in \mathbb{C}^{PN}$ is the noise vector with variance σ_w^2 and $\mathbf{Q} = (\mathbf{P}^\top \otimes \mathbf{I}_N) \in \mathbb{C}^{PN \times T}$, which depends only on the P -length sequence of complex pilots contained in $\mathbf{P} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times P}$.

III. ATOMIC NORM

We can define a sparse model as a linear combination of very few elements $\mathbf{u}_k \in \mathbb{C}^N$, also called atoms, defined as can be seen in (7) that belong within a structured and previously known atom set $\mathcal{U} = \{\mathbf{u}_1, \dots, \mathbf{u}_k, \dots\}$.

$$\mathbf{h} = \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_k \mathbf{u}_k \quad (7)$$

We have developed in the previous section the expression of the vectorized channel matrix $\mathbf{h}(\ell_{1:K}) = \sum_{k=1}^K \gamma_k \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{T}}(\ell_k)$ in order to appropriately represent the sparse nature of the mmWave band propagation. We can easily see that the structure of $\mathbf{h}(\ell_{1:K})$ is completely equivalent to the general expression of the atom model as seen in (7). The steering vector $\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{T}}(\ell_k)$, with the same structure seen in (3) for $\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{M}}$, is a d_l -Fourier parametrical atom set in which \mathbf{T} characterizes the total number of antennas and K is the number of elements, which is significantly smaller than the dimension of the model. This continuous atom set is going to be expressed as

$$\mathcal{U}^\ell = \{\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{T}}(\ell) : \ell \in \mathbb{T}^{d_l}\} \quad (8)$$

In order to solve the estimation problem regarding both the fading coefficients of the channel γ and the frequency set $\ell_{1:K} = \{\ell_1, \ell_2, \dots, \ell_K\}$ we are proposing a least squared approach regularized to consider the sparse structure of the channel vector $\mathbf{h}(\ell_{1:K})$ in (8). We can now define the ℓ_1 -norm that take into account the atom structure of $\mathbf{h}(\ell_{1:K})$.

Definition 1. Given a T -dimensional vector \mathbf{h} , the ℓ_1 -atomic norm (AN) of \mathbf{h} is defined as:

$$\|\mathbf{h}\|_{\mathcal{U}^\ell, 1} = \inf_{\ell \in \mathbb{T}^{d_l}, \alpha_k \in \mathbb{C}} \left\{ \sum_k |\alpha_k| : \mathbf{h} = \sum_k \alpha_k \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{T}}(\ell_k) \right\}.$$

Finally, we provide the novel optimization approach for parametrical low-key channel estimation that uses minimization of the atomic norm subject to a least squared function of the estimation error. We will show later that this approach not only provide the propagation parameters of the model, but also provided a whole estimate of the channel vector $\hat{\mathbf{h}}$:

$$\min_{\mathbf{h} \in \mathbb{C}^T} \|\mathbf{h}\|_{\mathcal{U}^\ell} \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \|\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{h} - \mathbf{y}\|_2^2 \leq \sigma_w^2 \quad (\text{P.1})$$

A. Atomic Norm-based optimization

In order to solve the optimization problem presented in (P.1), we are going to apply a convex optimization approach, based on the trace of a matrix with a certain known structure called a multi-level Toeplitz (MLT) matrix as in [21].

Since the trace of a matrix is a linear operator, we can solve our problem using the aforementioned structured matrix, that we name as $\mathbf{T}_{\mathbf{T}}$, belonging to the set $\mathcal{T}_{d_l} \subseteq \mathbb{C}^{T \times T}$ of all SPD d_l -MLT matrices so that $\mathbf{T}_{d_l} \geq \mathbf{T}_{d_l-1} \geq \dots \geq \mathbf{T}_1$, which implies that the term $\min_{\mathbf{h} \in \mathbb{C}^T} \|\mathbf{h}\|_{\mathcal{U}^\ell, 1}$ of the original expression (P.1) can be replaced as can be seen:

$$\min_{t, \mathbf{h} \in \mathbb{C}^T, \mathbf{T}_{\mathbf{T}} \in \mathcal{T}_{d_l}} \frac{1}{2}t + \frac{1}{2} \text{Tr}\{\mathbf{T}_{\mathbf{T}}\} \quad (\text{P.2})$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{T}_{\mathbf{T}} & \mathbf{h} \\ \mathbf{h}^H & t \end{bmatrix} \succeq 0$$

Using this expression we can finally obtain the estimation of the channel vector $\hat{\mathbf{h}}$. Furthermore, using [21, Alg. 1] we could decompose matrix $\mathbf{T}_{\mathbf{T}}$ solution of (P.3) in order to recover the parameter set $\hat{\ell}_{1:K}$ and the fading coefficients $\hat{\gamma}$.

Therefore, we propose to address (P.1) by adding to (P.2) the noise level constraint as follows

$$\min_{t, \mathbf{h} \in \mathbb{C}^T, \mathbf{T}_{\mathbf{T}} \in \mathcal{T}_{d_l}} \frac{1}{2}t + \frac{1}{2} \text{Tr}\{\mathbf{T}_{\mathbf{T}}\} \quad (\text{P.3})$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{T}_{\mathbf{T}} & \mathbf{h} \\ \mathbf{h}^H & t \end{bmatrix} \succeq 0, \quad \|\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{h} - \mathbf{y}\|_2^2 \leq \sigma_w^2$$

to obtain an estimate of the vectorized channel matrix $\hat{\mathbf{h}}$. In section V we will evaluate this approach and compare its results with other benchmarks in the literature.

IV. BENCHMARKS

The number of arithmetic operations needed in order to solve a semidefinite problem always depend on the dimension of the variable to be optimized n , the number of constraints m and the accuracy parameter ϵ as we can see in its complexity expression $O(m(n^3 + mn^2 + m^2)\sqrt{n} \log(1/\epsilon))$ [22]. Taking this into account, the complexity of our proposed semidefinite optimization problem, as seen in (P.3), can be defined as $O(T^{3.5})$

There are several state-of-the-art methods that aim to solve channel estimation problems. Three of the methods used as benchmarks for comparisons in this work are on-grid methods, which means that they depend on a predefined dictionary, so there is always some margin of error by its definition. On-grid methods are a valid comparison when the dictionary is defined with a granularity that allows the complexity of each algorithm to be equivalent with the complexity of the atomic norm optimization.

The on-grid algorithms used in order to make some valid comparisons in different scenarios are orthogonal matching pursuit (OMP), multiple signal classification (MUSIC) and adaptive matched filter with iterative interference cancellation (IIC-AMF). For each one we have predefined a grid or dictionary that makes their computational complexity equal to ours.

A. Multiple Signal Classification (MUSIC)

In conventional MUSIC algorithm [23], the covariance matrix of signal \mathbf{h} is estimated with respect to the observation $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{Q}\mathbf{h} + \mathbf{w}$ and then split between signal and noise taking into account the K most significant eigenvalues. The noise spectrum function is built upon a predefined grid and then it is used to estimate the frequencies by locating the peaks of the function.

The version of MUSIC that we have applied in this work as benchmark uses a Hankel matrix of d_l dimensions with $H < T$ [24].

Figure 1. MSE for $\mathbf{M} = [4]$, $\mathbf{N} = [4, 6]$ of channel estimation for $P = 3$ (a) $K = 2$, (b) $K = 3$, (c) $K = 4$.

Figure 2. MSE for $\mathbf{M} = [4]$, $\mathbf{N} = [4, 6]$ of channel estimation for SNR=20 (a) $K = 2$, (b) $K = 3$, (c) $K = 4$.

B. Orthogonal Matching Pursuit OMP

OMP algorithm [25] uses K iterations, until the K entries are found, in order to find the frequency vectors $\ell_{1:K}$. Each iteration uses the grid to find the best match to the residual of the observations $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{Q}\mathbf{h} + \mathbf{w}$. Finally, the dictionary entry is added to the support estimate and removed from the dictionary, updating the residual in the process.

C. Iterative interference cancellation

Originally, this on-grid method is based on a nonparametric weighted least-squares algorithm [26], [27]. Another approach [28] extracts one-by-one the prospective component atoms after removing the interference caused by the stronger detected signal components.

D. Non-parametrical methods: Least Squares and Minimum Mean Square Error

Least squares and minimum mean square error methods are traditional approaches to the channel estimation problem. Since all the statistics of the channel vector are known, we can apply the latter method as well.

Although both methods should be equivalent at high SNR, it must be taken into account the dimensions of the \mathbf{Q} matrix, which is only invertible when $PN = T$, and therefore in the rest of cases the equivalence does not hold.

V. RESULTS

The general scenario that we are considering in this work is built upon a uniform linear array deployment with $M = 4$ antennas at the transmitter with $\mathbf{M} = [\mathbf{M}_1] = [4]^T$ and $N = 24$ $\mathbf{N} = [\mathbf{N}_1, \mathbf{N}_2]^T = [4, 6]^T$ at the receiver.

Several number of scatters are considered $K \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6\}$ that will particularize the channel parame-

ters $\ell_k = [-\mathbf{g}_k^\top, \mathbf{f}_k^\top]^\top$. Several lengths of pilot sequences $P \in \{2, 3, 4\}$, that built the \mathbf{P} matrix, have also been considered. All the pilots are randomly-generated complex numbers. Several values of SNR have also been used in all the simulations, within a range from -10 to 100 .

Figure 1 shows the mean-square-error (MSE) of the estimation of the full channel vector $\hat{\mathbf{h}}$. We can easily check that the proposed atomic norm-based optimization method (P.3) outperforms the other five state-of-the-art methods for any given value of SNR and any number of scatters K .

In the set of graphics presented in Figure 2 we can see the behaviour of the channel estimation with respect the length of the known pilot sequence utilized in the transmission. For any value of P , the proposed method works better than any of the other techniques, including the cases with very short sequences such as $P = 2$.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This work proposes a gridless method for the resolution of the channel matrix estimation problem using atomic norm in order to model the sparsity in the mmWave band.

We propose a different optimization approach that avoid the typical off-line optimization of the convex parameter that regularizes the contribution of the Atomic norm versus the estimation error. The proposed technique has been compared with several state-of-the-art on-grid algorithms, obtaining better results for the estimation of the channel matrix regardless the values of the different variables in the proposed noisy scenario, such as the number of scatters K and the length of the transmitted pilot sequence P .

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